

DEVELOPMENT OF SYSTEMS OF PROFESSIONAL-ORIENTED TRAINING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF SUBJECT-WRITTEN INTEGRATION

Sharopova Shahlo Kahramonovna

assistant

Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural
Mechanization Engineers of Bukhara branch

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the problem of developing a system of professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages in a technical university on the basis of subject-language integration in our country and abroad. Based on the analysis of the functioning of this system, the goals and objectives are highlighted, as well as approaches to solving the formation and development of communicative foreign language competencies in modern students. The leading direction in the development of the system of professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages is the organization of integration both in relation to the content of interdisciplinary information and the methods of its assimilation.

There is no doubt that the subject-disciplinary approach to teaching foreign languages (FL) and basic professional disciplines is being replaced by an interdisciplinary approach, which is implemented in subject-foreign language integration. At the same time, from our point of view, the international experience of integrated teaching of a foreign language and specialty is important. This is a necessary condition for the training of future professionals who are able to become members of the international scientific and business community. The European educational program "English for special purposes" (ESP - English for special purposes) includes the following main points: language. A needs analysis is the basis for building ESP curricula to train FL

professionals in technical fields. The ESP course is being developed for an adult audience at the level of higher education, but it can be adapted for a secondary school [1, 25]. ESP is characterized by content, limited areas and models of professional communication, and on this foundation a highly specialized work program is developed. ESP working education programs are usually designed not only for students who speak a foreign language at an intermediate level (intermediate), but are adapted for students with a lower level of language proficiency. The program "English for Special Purposes" is developed and aimed at the formation of the correct use of grammatical and lexical skills with a specific professionally oriented purpose.

The main components of the ESP methodology should be distinguished: involvement (involvement), interaction (interaction), individualization (individualization), independence (independence). Involvement implies the active participation of students in all types of learning activities. Interaction is the basis of cooperation between the teacher and students, as well as between the students themselves in group work. Individualization means taking into account the manifestations of individual characteristics of students in teaching. Independence presupposes the ability of students to choose their own learning style [2, 234; 3, 92].

To introduce professionally-oriented work programs in the field of science-intensive disciplines into the educational process, it is necessary to work together with linguistic teachers and professionals in technical fields, where the following stages of interaction can be distinguished: cooperation, collaboration and team-teaching [4, 85].

And, finally, at the team-teaching stage, their joint work is embodied in the educational process. The teaching methodology of the ESP course and the teaching methodology of the basic English course (GE - General English) differ, first of all, in the relationship "teacher - student". The teacher is not the only primary source of knowledge of the subject and its expert (primary knower). The role of the trainer is characterized as the role of the manager of the educational process (manager), curator (facilitator), adviser (consultant). At the same time, the student has the opportunity to make his own decision regarding his own learning path. At the center of the procedure for assessing the achievements

of students in educational programs ESP is the professional foreign language and communicative competence, which are based on the ability to communicate in a foreign language in various situations [5, 24; 6, 73; 7, 160].

Subject-linguistic integration is reflected in the European educational program of subject-language integrated learning CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning). Foreign researchers talk about CLIL's orientation towards two goals - teaching a highly specialized subject and a foreign language, and the emphasis can shift from subject content to foreign language and, vice versa, depending on the task at hand. Achieving a dual goal requires the development of a special approach in which a non-linguistic subject is taught not just in a foreign language, but with the help or through a foreign language (vehicular language). The basic principles of CLIL include authenticity, multitasking, active subject acquisition, and scaffolding learning. The priority task of CLIL is the formation of subject-specific professional and foreign language competence and is used, as a rule, in primary and secondary schools [8, 30]. In accordance with the CLIL methodology, subject-language integration can be carried out in different ways:

- the study of foreign language is included in the curriculum for a special subject;
- the subject content is used in the classes on foreign language in the course of cooperation of the teachers of the above disciplines.

The main provisions of the CLIL methodology are based on four "c": - content - the content of the professional discipline included in the curriculum; - communication - oral and written communication in a foreign language

according to the profile of the specialty (communication in FL has a double purpose: on the one hand, to find a new way of teaching a foreign language, and on the other, to acquire knowledge in the field of a new subject discipline) [9,48]; - cognition (cognition) provides for the improvement of the cognitive abilities of students in the process of learning foreign language; - culture (culture) reflects the sociocultural context [10, 155; 11, 48].

As the goals of subject-language integrated learning, it is considered not only the mastery of knowledge in a special discipline, the formation of professional foreign language competence in a given subject area, but also the cognitive development of students, which is associated with operations. Training teachers using CLIL requires improving their linguistic, methodological and subject competencies. Assessment of students' achievements using the CLIL method implies, first of all, knowledge of the subject discipline. But it is the presence of a foreign language competence that will determine the feedback "student - teacher" in the assessment process. Also, the subject-language integration or mastery of students of both narrowly professional and linguistic competences is checked [12, 114].

According to the CLIL programs, the determination of the level of proficiency in a foreign language takes place within the framework of the CEFR. Subject to assessment:

- knowledge of terminological vocabulary in the field of professional communication;
- knowledge of a foreign language grammatical structure and the skill of owning it;

- communicative ability to adequately use functional linguistic structures in a discussion to express disagreement, doubt, support, correctly use indirect speech, etc.;
- communicative ability to reason on the FL and analyze the information received from various sources on the FL;
- the ability to effectively make a presentation of the results of project activities on a subject topic at the FIL [13, 17; 14, 55].

It should be emphasized that the main difference between ESP and CLIL is the nature of the relationship between the two components of interdisciplinary integration. Subject-thematic content forms the student's language competence in the developed ESP programs. The basis is the improvement of foreign language communication skills, the assessment is made of the knowledge of terminology, grammar and discourse features common to the natural-scientific professional sphere. While the task of CLIL is to teach professional discipline by means of a foreign language, and the dual purpose is pursued - to form students' knowledge of professional discipline and at the same time to develop their foreign language competence. According to CLIL, both the level of proficiency in subject competence and the level of proficiency in a foreign language competence are assessed.

The study of foreign approaches that are of interest for narrowly specialized technical or natural science education showed the need for further development of areas of subject-language integration related to the study of foreign languages for specialized purposes. The design of such an integrated learning process, including foreign languages and professional subject cycles, as well as the integration of cognitive and

educational activities, posed serious challenges to methodologists, foreign language teachers and subject teachers. The principle of integrativity should be given one of the leading roles. This principle is reflected in the implementation of the training program for future specialists as a complex process for the development of professional language competence in close relationship with knowledge in the field of professional disciplines on the basis of integration both in relation to the content of interdisciplinary information and methods its assimilation. The unifying link is a foreign language as a tool for mastering professional communication [15, 65]. Professional linguistic competence is the basis for professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages, which must be considered as a logical unity and a clear correlation of managerial, linguistic and professionally oriented knowledge, skills and abilities, operating with foreign language material for professional goals. If the ESP tasks, one way or another, were considered by the working training programs of technical universities, then the CLIL tasks were considered erroneous until recently.

Summing up, we update our attention on the main provisions presented in this article.

1. When analyzing the functioning of the system of professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages in a technical university on the basis of subject-language integration in our country and abroad, the goals and objectives, as well as approaches to their solution, facing the system are highlighted

2. Based on the analysis of trends and priority directions of development of the system of professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages in a technical university, it is shown that at the current stage, the organization of integration becomes the leading direction both in relation to the content of interdisciplinary information and ways to assimilate it. The unifying link is a foreign language as a tool for mastering professional communication

3. It is shown that the development of a system of professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages in a technical university is impossible without subject-language integration.

The ideas of subject-linguistic integration are of great importance both for theoretical research and for the practical implementation of the ESP process in technical higher educational institutions.

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